

Widening participation in data science: implementing policy for well-being in the workplace

Authors¹

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Summary of the Work

People in **data science**² work under high-pressure conditions, such as dealing with complex projects, tight deadlines, precarious contracts and large numbers of collaborators working across different contexts. This led to the authors, who are researchers in data-intensive fields, selecting **mental health and well-being** as a one of themes in this project. In this work, we applied a diversity, equity, inclusion and accessibility (DEI&A) lens onto the topic of mental well-being at the workplace for “widening participation”. We conducted an initial policy review, exploratory interviews with OLS community members about workplace difficulties and **resilience**, and built upon those results through a group well-being intervention based on a support tool known as “Tree of Life”. Common challenges included lack of clarity, and training, communication issues, while

coping strategies highlighted **peer support**. **Bottom-up** initiatives and virtual communities do have potential for nurturing well-being through advocacy and support for their members.

Key Findings

“*People in data science*” can be found in higher education (students, lifelong learners), academia (graduate and postgraduate researchers), industry (experts, managers). Employers and educational institutions have a duty of care to ensure safety and health (including mental health) for their staff and students.

Mental well-being at the workplace and academia

According to [Mental Health UK's annual burnout report for 2023](#), 9 in 10 adults in the UK experienced extreme levels of stress, with 1 in 5 having to take time off work due to poor mental health caused by work-related stress.

Poor mental health is rampant in academia as well - “[fed up and burnt out](#)” ([Evans et al., 2018](#)). Research on mental health problems among UK researchers demonstrates among all that students and researchers from minority backgrounds report poorer mental health, including suffering from **impostor phenomenon** (e.g. [Hazell et al., 2021](#), [Cristea and Babajide, 2022](#), [Milicev et al., 2023](#)). This implies that institutional efforts to improve wellbeing should include strategies to promote equality,

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² Terms in **green and bold** are in the Glossary

diversity, resilience, integration, social support, and work-life balance.

Policy review in the topics related to the DEI&A and mental well-being in the UK higher education system revealed a number of useful and powerful frameworks, such as:

- [Race Equality Charter](#), which addresses institutional and cultural barriers in the way of ethnic minority staff and students;
- [The Athena Swan Charter](#), which aims to support and transform gender equality within higher education and research;
- [Stepchange: Mentally Healthy Universities](#), which calls on universities to prioritise the mental health of their students and staff by taking a "whole-university" approach to mental health.

Among the risks associated with implementation of multiple charters and frameworks, it is important to mention administrative burden for applicants.

Our research on **bottom-up organisations - stakeholders in the UK** revealed an outstanding example to be [Students Minds'](#) advocacy work. It grew from a student-led support group for students experiencing mental health difficulties at university to developing dedicated student support programmes, setting up a [University Mental Health Charter](#) and providing a voluntary accreditation scheme for universities.

Other examples of bottom-up initiatives relating to **mental health in academia** include a collection of international stories by the ["Voices of Academia"](#) initiative, mental health training programmes developed "by academics for academics" offered by non-profit

[Dragonfly Mental Health. ReMO COST Action CA19117: "Researcher Mental Health"](#) is an interdisciplinary research network, bringing together research, practice, advocacy and policy ([Kismihók et al 2021](#)). These initiatives help raise awareness about the topic, reduce the stigma and provide educational resources.

Virtual support of communities of concerns and communities of practice

Examples of advocacy and networking are given by communities of concerns, e.g. [Women in Academia Support Network #WIASN](#). It aims to provide support and networking to women academics that may not be available to them in their workplaces. *R-Ladies* is a global open source community promoting female R (programming language) practitioners and learners. This community, like many other bottom-up initiatives, devised a **Code of Conduct** to foster inclusive behaviours and prevent harassment. Finally, [Team Neurodiversity of FORRT \(Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training\)](#) provides **neurodivergent** scholars opportunities to address **ableism** in academia through work to promote open scholarship.

[OLS](#) is a virtual community of practice built by members from across the globe. OLS devised a training program in open research with strong focus on inclusiveness and equity, with a respective Code of Conduct. Within its training program OLS includes regular co-working sessions, virtual social gatherings, [Ally Skills training](#) and dedicated sessions on mental well-being and self-care.

Inputs from the OLS community

We conducted qualitative research among OLS community members regarding work-related challenges and coping strategies, with the UK being the most represented among the various countries involved.

In summary, the risks to well-being related to:

(1) Workload and work environment

- Excessive workload
- Frequent context switching
- Lack of onboarding processes
- Unspoken rules and expectations
- Lack of clarity in goals

(2) Interpersonal communication

- Bullying and power abuse
- ineffective communication with supervisors

(3) Lack of appropriate training opportunities

(4) Loneliness, especially for expats and immigrants

Consequences included frequent sick leave, "[quiet quitting](#)", and leaving the job.

When asked about ***coping strategies and resilience factors***, the following skills were revealed: being pragmatic and determined; proactive in seeking information and solutions; continuous improvement and learning; self-education and self-awareness.

Peer support, whether self-organised teams or groups organised by institutions, appeared on many occasions as an important and valuable coping mechanism and source of support against difficulties.

These results are in line with the existing growing pool of research on the experiences of mental health and well-being of academic researchers ([Nicholls et al., 2022](#), [Milicev et al., 2023](#)).

Pilot intervention: OLS well-being workshop:

We used the Tree of Life psychosocial support tool ([Ncube, 2006](#), [Parham et al., 2019](#)) to run a pilot intervention within the OLS community, with intentions to bring people in data science together in a safe space to share and document their knowledge about coping strategies. Survey results showed that 2 in 3 of the recruited participants are at risk of work-related burnout, and when people believed more in their own abilities (their agency), they tended to experience less burnout.

The intervention appeared to be promising in reminding people about their values, connectedness to others and community. To culminate, we constructed a *collective document* which combined individual and collective experiences, highlighting topics of safeguarding younger professionals, advocacy, connection, hope and unitedness in adversities. Circulating this document in data science-active communities and gathering the resonances will help to connect people and raise their collective resilience.

Recommendations

Mental health issues and resilience are often viewed individually, while common phenomena such as burnout syndrome or impostor phenomena are context- and environment- dependent. **Interventions to increase resilience should not overemphasise individual**

responsibilities whilst neglecting to address systemic barriers and inequalities.

Based on the results of the research and intervention, we can formulate the following *recommendations*:

1) Promote well-being and inclusive practices at work:

- Promote work-life balance and **flexible** arrangements
- Establish **onboarding programs** to familiarise new personnel with culture of the organisation, expectations and career development opportunities and aid social integration
- Offer tailored skill development, training sessions, and resources

2) Facilitate communication and feedback mechanisms

- Encourage organisation-wide **clarity in communication**, with regular updates and retrospective feedbacks
- Create mechanisms to **gather feedback** from the employees / students around well-being
- Develop guidelines / **codes of conduct for acceptable behaviour** (inclusive, kind, non-judgemental) and unacceptable ones (bullying and harassment) with robust reporting procedures

3) Foster bottom up and peer initiatives

- Encourage and support horizontal collaboration, bottom-up initiatives, such as student- or employee- led peer support groups by providing funding and other resources

Glossary

Ableism refers to a type of discrimination, that favours non-disabled people.

Ally skills in the workplace refer to being able to use personal privilege to support colleagues from less privileged or marginalised groups

Bottom-up refers to ideas or initiatives that originate from the lower levels of an organisation or society and move upwards.

Burnout syndrome is a syndrome resulting from chronic workplace stress. It manifests through physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion.

Code of Conduct refers to a set of rules that outline the norms, responsibilities, and practices of a community or organisation, including procedures and outcomes for reporting violations.

Communities of Concerns (CoCs) are often used to refer to groups of people, in particular from marginalised groups, facing and addressing specific social, environmental or political challenges.

Community of Practice (CoPs) is a group of people with common interest, profession, or expertise, who gather to learn, share knowledge, and collaborate in a structured way.

Coping strategies are thoughts and actions that people employ to handle difficult situations.

Data science is an academic discipline and professional field which uses interdisciplinary techniques to manipulate and analyse data.

Impostor phenomenon refers to the feeling of being inadequate despite evident success, commonly experienced by high achievers such as academics.

Mental health refers to feeling good, being able to handle ups and down, working productively, and giving back to the community.

Neurodivergent and neurodiversity, refers to the natural range of differences in how people's brains work, e.g. how they socialise, learn, focus and feel.

Peer support is when people use their own experiences to help each other. Usually views and experiences of participants are equally valued.

Resilience is related to skills that influence good individual and community health outcomes, in spite of negative events and threats. Supportive environments are instrumental to resilience.